

RANSOMWARE RISK IN DIGITAL ECOSYSTEMS OF SMEs: ECONOMIC COSTS, OPERATIONAL DISRUPTIONS, AND BUSINESS CONTINUITY

TOMISLAV JAKOPEC

Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek, Croatia.
Email: tjakopec@ffos.hr; ORCID: orcid.org/0000-0001-8038-3002

MILAN PUVAČA

Ofir d.o.o., Osijek, Croatia. Email: milan@ofir.hr; ORCID: orcid.org/0000-0003-0056-5290

Abstract

This study examines the economic consequences of ransomware for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) within digital business ecosystems. As SMEs increasingly rely on cloud platforms and shared IT infrastructure, ransomware has evolved into a systemic economic shock capable of cascading across the ecosystem. Existing literature often focuses on large organizations, leaving a gap regarding SME resource constraints and structural vulnerabilities, particularly in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE). To address this, the study develops a framework based on the resource-based view (RBV) and dynamic capabilities. It explains why SMEs suffer disproportionately due to a lack of tangible resources and higher-order capabilities for threat monitoring and post-incident learning. Using reflexive thematic analysis on 88 sources, the study identifies five key themes: operational disruption, financial burden, reputational damage, business continuity fragility, and ecosystem coordination deficits. Each theme explores subthemes such as the gap between insured and uninsured firms and the discrepancy between individual and ecosystem-level resilience. The paper concludes with five propositions and differentiated implications for SME governance, insurers, and policymakers. It emphasizes that building resilience requires collective coordination rather than individual firm investments, which is critical in the CEE context where rapid digitalization has outpaced cybersecurity maturity.

Keywords: Ransomware; Digital Ecosystems of SMEs; Economic Costs; Operational Disruption; Organizational Resilience;

JEL Classification: L26, M15, D81, O33, G32

INTRODUCTION

The digital transformation of European economies has reshaped the way SMEs create and deliver value. Cloud-based business platforms, managed IT services, third-party payment service providers, and digitally mediated supply chains now form the foundation of the daily operations of millions of firms (Jacobides et al., 2018; Nambisan et al., 2019). Participation in such an ecosystem enables SMEs to access technologies and markets that until recently were only feasible for large corporations. At the same time, it introduces a new form of systemic risk: the spread of cyber threats through interconnected nodes, of which ransomware has become the most economically damaging (Razaulla et al., 2023).

SMEs represent more than 50% of all businesses in the European Union, they employ approximately two-thirds of the private sector workforce, and account for more than half of the total value added (Di Bella, L. et al., 2023). In CEE, SMEs play a particularly critical role as drivers of employment and market development. Digital transformation in the

region has accelerated since the mid-2010s, spurred by EU structural funds and the growth of outsourced IT services (OECD, 2023). However, this acceleration has been uneven. Many SMEs in CEE have adopted digital tools without adequate investments in cybersecurity management, creating a gap between digital exposure and organizational readiness (ENISA, 2024). When ransomware disrupts an SME that serves as a data supplier or processor within a broader ecosystem, the damage cascades to partners, customers, and the ecosystem as a whole (Bahmanova & Lace, 2025).

Despite the economic significance of this issue, the scientific literature has not addressed it in a systematic way. Information security research favours technical countermeasures over business impact analysis (Sittig & Singh, 2016). The literature on the economics of cybercrime is oriented toward the contexts of large companies (Abrardi, L., Comino, S., & Grassini, S., 2025). The business continuity literature has been slow to incorporate ransomware-specific dynamics (Fani & Subriadi, 2019). Few existing studies explain why SMEs suffer disproportionately; instead, they merely note that this is the case (Connolly, L. Y. et al., 2020). This gap is wider for CEE, where corporate-level cybersecurity data remains scarce (Šafár, L., Sopko, J., & Meš'an, M, 2026).

This study attempts to address the gap by developing a framework of economic consequences based on a firm's RBV (Barney, 1991) and the perspective of dynamic capabilities (Teece, 2007). RBV explains which resource deficits make SMEs structurally more vulnerable. The dynamic capabilities perspective explains how these firms struggle to recognize threats, provide an effective response, and learn from incidents. The study was guided by three research questions: (RQ1) What are the main economic costs that ransomware imposes on SMEs in digital ecosystems, and through which mechanisms are hidden costs accumulated? (RQ2) How does ransomware-induced disruption cascade through the digital ecosystems of SMEs and which structural characteristics amplify or mitigate this effect? (RQ3) How do business continuity preparedness and organizational resilience intertwine at the level of the firm and the ecosystem?

Methodologically, this study applies reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006; 2019) on a corpus of 88 sources. Five propositions are presented. The paper concludes with differentiated implications for practitioners and policymakers, with attention to conditions in CEE.

1. Review of the scientific literature

1.1 Participation of SMEs in digital ecosystems

The digital ecosystem encompasses a network of digitally connected stakeholders who jointly produce value through shared infrastructure and data flows (Jacobides et al., 2018). For SMEs, this means the economics of competition is changing: cloud platforms reduce fixed costs, service providers manage IT infrastructure, and digital supply chains extend market reach (Nambisan et al., 2019). These dependencies also reshape the risk profile. A disruption in any node can spread throughout the ecosystem. The literature on ecosystems has devoted considerable attention to value creation and management, but relatively little to the systemic risks introduced by interconnections (Adner, 2017).

In CEE, the sharing economy within the ecosystem adds an extra layer of complexity. Many SMEs have rapidly adopted digital tools, often relying on more cost-effective SaaS (Software as a Service) solutions or using IT services from regional or international providers (OECD, 2023). Although this has brought competitive advantages, it has created dependence on suppliers whose security practices SMEs can only limitedly influence. Furthermore, the institutional infrastructure supporting cybersecurity in CEE remains weaker than in Western Europe: fewer CERTs (Computer Emergency Response Teams) serve the SME sector, threat-sharing initiatives are less mature, and affordable cyber insurance is more limited (ENISA, 2024). The EU NIS2 Directive (Directive 2022/2555) expands obligations to SMEs in critical sectors, but questions remain about how resource-constrained firms in CEE will meet the new requirements without proportional institutional support.

1.2 Ransomware as an economic threat at the ecosystem level

Ransomware has evolved into an organized criminal industry characterized by targeted attacks, double and triple extortion, and ransomware-as-a-service (RaaS) (Beaman et al., 2021). RaaS partners are increasingly targeting SMEs, which are perceived as likely payers and are unlikely to have strong defences (Chainalysis, 2024). Europol also confirms that ransomware remains the most expensive form of cybercrime, with record numbers of attacks in 2024 (Europol, 2024). When ransomware strikes a service provider, it simultaneously affects every client and service partner of an SME. When it strikes an SME in the digital supply chain, it causes data flow disruptions, triggers contractual penalties, and undermines partner trust (Cartwright et al., 2023). In CEE, where many SMEs serve as external suppliers within pan-European value chains, cascading potential is significant, although evidence on a firm's level remains limited.

1.3 Theoretical framework: RBV and Dynamic Capabilities

RBV claims that competitive advantage depends on the resources that are valuable, rare, imperfectly imitable, and not substitutable (Barney, 1991). When applied to cybersecurity, RBV reveals an asymmetry: large companies have dedicated security teams (at least an IT department), incident response testing plans, and financial reserves. SMEs generally lack such portfolio (Heidt et al., 2019; Alahmari & Duncan, 2020).

SMEs should be able to leverage dynamic capabilities and expand the RBV by focusing on threat identification, seizing opportunities, and reorganizing resources (Teece, 2007). In the context of ransomware, sensing translates into threat monitoring and early warning capabilities; seizing involves implementing countermeasures and making time-critical decisions; reorganization involves learning from incidents and management adaptation. SMEs perform poorly in all three areas (Duchek, 2020). The combination of capabilities yields a fundamental analytical claim: ransomware creates disproportionate consequences for SMEs not only because they have fewer resources, but because they lack the organizational capacity to adaptively use those resources. Each incident drains an already scarce resource base, creating a self-reinforcing cycle of vulnerability.

1.4 Economic impacts and business continuity

Economic impacts at the firm level documented in recent literature (Florackis et al., 2023) show that cyber incidents cause a significant drop in a firm's value, with smaller firms suffering proportionally greater losses. Kamiya et al. (2021) find that cyberattacks undermine customer trust and increase the cost of capital. Romanosky (2016) demonstrates that indirect costs typically far exceed direct costs. The cascading ecosystem-level costs borne by partners that were not direct targets remain poorly measured by existing frameworks (Cartwright et al., 2023). Business continuity management (BCM) enables firms to restore critical functions after a disruption (Torabi et al., 2016). Organizational resilience expands BCM to include a firm's broader adaptive capacity (Duchek, 2020). SMEs perform poorly on both dimensions (Herbane, 2010). Ecosystem-level resilience depends on coordination mechanisms, including threat sharing and collective response, which remain underdeveloped, especially in CEE (OECD, 2023; ENISA, 2024). The central unresolved question is whether deeper embedding in the ecosystem enhances resilience or increases fragility.

2. Research Methodology

2.1 Research framework

The study adopts a qualitative literature-based framework using reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006; 2019). This approach was chosen because the relevant literature spans multiple disciplines and has not been synthesized from the perspective of ecosystem-oriented SMEs. There are certain practical limitations to collecting primary data from ransomware-affected SMEs. First, the topic is highly sensitive and there is a fear of reputational damage, which leads organizations to avoid acknowledging the incident so as not to undermine client trust and market reputation. Additionally, firms fear that sharing data with researchers could result in regulatory penalties, or the priority of quickly restoring systems to operational status often leads to the unintentional deletion of key digital evidence and traces of the attack (Connolly, L. Y. et al., 2020). At the same time, the literature has reached a sufficient volume to support interpretive synthesis. Following Braun & Clarke's (2019) approach, the literature was analysed through coding, with the priority being to achieve a meaningful and logical interpretation of the data. Instead of statistical measurement of agreement between multiple coders, an in-depth qualitative analysis was prioritized.

2.2 Search protocol and corpus composition

The literature search was conducted in February 2026, covering the Scopus database (n=214), Web of Science (n=168), Google Scholar (n=347), and specialized sources including IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect, and the repositories of ENISA, OECD, Europol, and the World Economic Forum (n=98). The time window covered the period from January 2016 to February 2026. The basic search string was defined as: (“ransomware” OR “cyber extortion”) AND (“SME” OR “small business” OR “small enterprise”) AND (“economic” OR “cost” OR “disruption” OR “continuity” OR “resilience” OR “digital ecosystem”). The process was further refined by applying specific syntaxes for each

database: in the Scopus database, a string used was TITLE-ABS-KEY((ransomware OR "cyber extortion") AND (SME OR "small business" OR "small enterprise") AND (economic OR cost OR disruption OR continuity OR resilience OR "digital ecosystem")) AND PUBYEAR > 2015. For Web of Science, TS=((ransomware OR "cyber extortion") AND (SME OR "small business" OR "small enterprise") AND (economic OR cost OR disruption OR continuity OR resilience OR "digital ecosystem")) was applied, with a time limit 2016–2026. The search in Google Scholar primarily focused on allintitle: ransomware SME economic OR cost OR disruption OR continuity OR resilience, with additional keyword variations and filtering by date. In the IEEE Xplore / ScienceDirect databases, a string used was ((ransomware) AND (SME OR "small business") AND (economic OR cost OR disruption OR resilience)) for the period 2016–2026. Finally, targeted searches were conducted in the institutional repositories of ENISA, the OECD, Europol, and the WEF using the following terms: ransomware, SME, cybersecurity, digital ecosystem, economic impact. The search returned 827 records. After removing 278 duplicates, 549 records passed the title and abstract screening, of which 397 were excluded as being out of scope. Analysis of 152 records excluded 73 (31 purely technical, 22 solely about large companies, 20 low quality or outdated). Backward citation tracking added another 9 sources, yielding a final corpus of 88 articles. The articles are in the following categories: 56 journal articles, 17 institutional reports, 8 book chapters, and 7 conference papers (Figure no. 1; Table no. 1). Peer-reviewed articles (resulting from a peer-review process) carry analytical claims; institutional reports serve a contextual and statistical function.

Figure no. 1: Literature search and selection process

Table no. 1: Corpus composition (n = 88)

Source type	2016–20	2021–23	2024–26	Total	Role in analysis
Journal articles	9	21	26	56	Analytical and causal claims
Institutional reports	2	5	10	17	Context, statistics, trends
Book chapters	3	4	1	8	Conceptual grounding
Proceedings	2	3	2	7	Emerging evidence
Total	16	33	39	88	

Source: Authors' research protocol

2.3 Thematic analysis procedure

The analysis consists of six phases (Braun & Clarke, 2006; 2019). In Phase 1 (familiarization), all 88 sources were familiarized by taking descriptive and interpretive notes recorded in a structured journal. In Phase 2 (coding), each analytically relevant part was assigned one or more code labels in a spreadsheet-based system. A total of 310 codes were generated, including labels such as "downtime varies by backup quality," "flat network architecture increases blast radius", "insurance exclusions limit coverage," "post-incident review rarely conducted in small firms", "managed service provider compromise affects multiple clients", "high recovery costs", "direct recovery expenditure" and "hidden cost accumulation" because the difference has become analytically significant.

In the Phase 3, the codes were grouped according to similarity into candidate themes:

- Operational disruption and cascading spread across the ecosystem
- Direct financial burden and hidden recovery costs
- Reputational damage and erosion of trust in the ecosystem
- Business continuity fragility
- Organizational resilience and ecosystem coordination deficits

In Phase 4, the themes were reviewed for internal coherence and representativeness; one candidate theme ("regulatory consequences") was disbanded because its codes functioned better as enhancers within other themes. In Phase 5, each theme was named, delineated, and linked to subthemes and internal tensions. In Phase 6, the results and discussion were integrated (Section 3).

3. Results

A reflexive thematic analysis of a corpus of 88 sources generated unique codes describing the economic realities of SMEs facing ransomware. These data were systematized into five main themes (T1–T5) that form the backbone of the research findings.

The themes are presented in the following graphical and tabular formats (Figure no. 2; Table no. 2), and each is analysed in more detail in the discussion.

Figure no. 2: From digital ecosystem dependence to economic consequences of ransomware in SMEs

Table no. 2: Thematic findings with subthemes, tensions, and theoretical linkages

Theme	Key dimensions	Subthemes/ tensions	SME implications	Theoretical lens
T1: Disruption	System lock; cascading	Ecosystem amplification vs attenuation (P1); secondary productivity loss	Flat architectures; lean staffing	RBV: limited redundancy; DC: reconfiguring (P1)
T2: Financial burden	Direct + hidden costs	Insured vs uninsured (P2); ransom dilemma	Thin margins; existential threat	RBV: resource scarcity; DC: seizing failure
T3: Trust erosion	Client defection; brand harm	Regulated vs unregulated; ecosystem trust (P3)	Small client base; data exposure	DC: weak sensing of reputational signals
T4: Continuity fragility	Untested BCP; backup gaps	Standalone vs embedded; awareness gap (P4)	External obligations vs internal resources	DC: sensing-seizing failure
T5: Resilience deficits	Governance; learning; coordination	Individual vs ecosystem resilience (P5); learning deficit	Security as cost centre	DC: reconfiguring failure; ecosystem gap

Note: RBV = resource-based view; DC = dynamic capabilities; P = proposition. Source: Authors' research protocol

The results show that cascading effects within the supply chain render a firm's individual defence insufficient if system-wide mechanisms fail. The results pertain to the context of Central and Eastern Europe, where specific risks have been identified arising from rapid digitalization alongside a simultaneous lag in institutional support and the maturity of threat data-sharing systems. As a direct analytical output from these themes, the research formulated five propositions that link the theoretical constructs of the resource approach and dynamic capabilities with the identified empirical gaps in SMEs' practice.

3.1 Theme 1: Operational disruption and cascading spread throughout the ecosystem

The immediate consequence of ransomware is the disruption of core operations. Centralized IT architectures and the lack of failover systems in SMEs mean that a single attack can compromise an entire firm's digital environment (Heidt et al., 2019). The dimension of the digital ecosystem generates a specific multiplier effect: the moment ransomware compromises the integrity and availability of data, it disrupts critical information flows to partners in the chain. This blockade causes a cascading disruption that correlates with the level of network connectivity, extending operational downtime far beyond the primary perimeter of the attacked organization. Cartwright et al. (2023) show that total network losses exceed the sum of individual firm losses due to the effects of interdependence. In CEE, where many SMEs act as external suppliers within pan-European chains, a single event can reach end-clients in Western Europe, although empirical documentation remains limited.

The literature also identifies secondary productivity losses that persist even after the system's nominal restoration. People have to recreate lost work, re-enter data, and cope with psychological stress (Cheng, 2022). Through the lens of dynamic capabilities, this prolonged recovery reflects a weak ability to reorganize: the firm cannot quickly reallocate its people and systems into a functional configuration. The duration of this secondary phase is poorly measured in existing research that tends to focus on the initial downtime window, resulting in a systematic underestimation of the total cost of disruption.

3.2 Theme 2: Direct financial burden and hidden recovery costs

Financial costs extend beyond the ransom itself and include forensic investigation, hardware replacement, legal counsel, lost revenue, customer churn, and increased insurance premiums (Florackis et al., 2023; Romanosky, 2016). Through the lens of RBV, this burden is amplified in SMEs because of resource slack. The gap between insured and uninsured firms represents significant tension. (Franke, 2017) and Woods & Böhme (2021) show that insured firms recover faster, but adoption of insurance among SMEs remains low, especially in CEE. Insurance primarily covers direct costs but does little to address reputational losses and loss of capacity.

The decision to pay a ransom is shaped by information asymmetry: an SME cannot verify whether the payment will result in functional decryption or prompt re-targeting (Cartwright et al., 2023). This represents a seizing failure within the framework of dynamic capabilities.

3.3 Theme 3: Reputational damage and erosion of trust in the ecosystem

Kamiya et al. (2021) demonstrate that cyberattacks erode customer trust and increase the cost of capital, with effects that persist even a year after the incident. The impact is shaped by the regulatory context: mandatory disclosure amplifies short-term reputational costs in regulated sectors but may spur higher baseline preparedness. The phenomenon of double extortion inflicts deep damage on trust within digital ecosystems, since data stolen from one provider of managed services (SME) directly compromises partners whose information was previously shared through legitimate business processes. Such a scenario creates negative external security (Laszka et al., 2017), which in a broader sense undermines trust among stakeholders and deters them from further data integration – a process on which the value creation of the entire ecosystem directly depends.

3.4 Theme 4: Business continuity fragility

SMEs demonstrate weaker business continuity management than large companies (Herbane, 2010). SMEs embedded in supply chains face continuity requirements from ecosystem partners (service level agreements, recovery time objectives) that can drive planning but increase its complexity, while standalone SMEs receive less external support. Many SME owners recognize the importance of continuity planning but fail to implement effective plans (Bada & Nurse, 2020). Through the lens of dynamic capabilities, this reflects a seizing failure: the firm feels threatened but cannot act due to conflicting pressures, resource scarcity, and a lack of guidance. In CEE, where public support for cybersecurity remains limited, this gap can be even wider.

3.5 Theme 5: Organizational resilience and ecosystem coordination deficits

The literature reveals resilience deficits at the technical, procedural, and strategic levels (Alahmari & Duncan, 2020; Duchek, 2020). The most analytically important tension is that between firm-level and ecosystem-level resilience. An SME can invest in its own defense and yet remain exposed through weaker ecosystem partners. Ecosystem-level mechanisms (threat intelligence sharing, coordinated response, collective insurance) could strengthen resilience at a lower cost per firm, but remain underdeveloped (OECD, 2023). In CEE, collaboration between firms on cybersecurity is in its infancy. Post-incident learning is often incomplete: SMEs often do not conduct reviews or invest in system improvements (Patterson et al., 2023), which represents a reconfiguration failure.

4. Discussion

Based on the results of the conducted analysis, the paper puts forward the following five propositions that serve as a foundation for understanding the economic dynamics of ransomware in the context of SMEs:

- Proposition 1. The disruption caused by ransomware in SMEs is amplified by embeddedness in an ecosystem when coordination mechanisms are weak, but can be mitigated when ecosystems provide a shared recovery infrastructure.

- Proposition 2. Cyber insurance reduces the immediate financial impact but does not significantly mitigate the indirect costs associated with reputation, trust, and positioning within the ecosystem.
- Proposition 3. Double extortion leads to the diffusion of distrust throughout the ecosystem, which directly deters partners from integrating and sharing data.
- Proposition 4. The gap between the awareness of the importance of business continuity and its actual application by SMEs reflects a failure of dynamic capabilities in the seizing phase. Therefore, this gap is more effectively addressed by reducing the costs of implementation itself, rather than solely by raising awareness.
- Proposition 5. Ecosystem-level resilience mechanisms reduce preparedness costs per firm and generate positive spillover effects that firm-level investments alone cannot achieve.

The interaction between SMEs and digital ecosystems, as suggested by the first proposition, creates a situation in which integration simultaneously offers competitive advantages and increases systemic vulnerability. The results indicate that under conditions of weak coordination mechanisms, connectivity becomes a channel for the cascading spread of operational disruption that exceeds the sum of individual firms' losses. Through the lens of the RBV, this burden is amplified in SMEs due to a lack of surplus resources, making every decision, including that of paying a ransom, critical for survival. While cyber insurance emerges as a tool for mitigating financial shock, another proposition highlights its limits in addressing reputational losses and the long-term erosion of partner trust. These indirect costs, according to the literature, often exceed direct recovery expenses but remain outside the focus of standard insurance policies.

An additional dimension of economic harm is manifested through the phenomenon of double extortion which, according to the third proposition, undermines the very essence of digital ecosystems' functioning – data exchange. When data stolen from one stakeholder compromises other partners, risk spills over to the rest of the participants, deterring firms from further integration and slowing value creation across the entire system. A similar barrier has been observed in business continuity management, where the fourth proposition argues that the gap in protection implementation is not a result of mere management ignorance, but reflects a failure in the “seizing” phase due to the high cost and complexity of implementing recovery plans. In the context of the CEE region, where insurance institutions and markets are less mature, these problems are even more pronounced, leaving SMEs at a disadvantage compared to their Western European counterparts.

Finally, the fifth proposition offers a solution by shifting the focus from individual to collective resilience. The results suggest that shared infrastructure, such as regional threat-sharing networks or coordinated response centres, can significantly lower the cost threshold for preparedness for individual SMEs. The synthesis through reinforcing feedback loops (Figure no. 3) confirms that without such systemic intervention, SMEs remain trapped in a cycle of fragility where each incident degrades the resources and

capabilities needed for future defence. This conclusion necessitates redefining cybersecurity from a technical cost to a fundamental working condition for participating in the digital economy, requiring a stronger role for legislators and public policymakers.

Figure no. 3: Reinforcing feedback loops among the five thematic dimensions

CONCLUSIONS

Ransomware no longer represents an isolated technical incident but a systemic economic shock that, through cascading mechanisms, destabilizes entire digital ecosystems of SMEs. This transformation redefines the cyber threat as a critical economic variable that directly jeopardizes resources, business continuity, and a company's very position within the value chain. SMEs bear disproportionate consequences due to limited resources and a lack of dynamic capabilities for timely detection, response, and post-incident learning. The literature highlights that Central and Eastern Europe is particularly vulnerable, where digital transformation has rapidly outpaced cybersecurity maturity. Operational disruptions within affiliated entities create effects that extend beyond the boundaries of individual firms. Such incidents impose direct financial burdens as well as enormous hidden recovery costs that drain resources. Consequently, there is profound reputational damage and erosion of trust among stakeholders. This exposes systemic fragilities in business continuity and serious deficits in resilience coordination across the entire system. The analysis identified five key themes: operational disruption and cascading spread across the ecosystem; direct financial burden and hidden recovery costs; reputational damage and erosion of trust in the ecosystem; business continuity fragility; and organizational resilience and ecosystem coordination deficits. These themes indicate

that the effects of ransomware extend beyond the individual firm and impact the entire ecosystem. The study's findings have yielded five propositions for understanding the economic dynamics of ransomware. First, disruptions are amplified by ecosystem connectivity but can be mitigated by shared infrastructure. Second, cyber insurance reduces direct costs but not indirect losses. Third, double extortion undermines trust and data exchange. Fourth, the business continuity gap stems from implementation limitations, not just a lack of awareness. Fifth, ecosystem-level resilience enables more effective risk management than individual approaches.

In the context of Central and Eastern Europe, these problems are more pronounced due to uneven digitalization and weaker institutional support. Therefore, the resilience of SMEs requires coordinated mechanisms at the ecosystem level, not just investments at the level of individual companies.

The disruption is further amplified by embeddedness in ecosystems when coordination mechanisms are weak, but shared infrastructure can significantly mitigate these effects. Although cyber insurance reduces the immediate financial blow, it does not address the loss of reputation and market position. The phenomenon of double extortion spreads distrust and directly deters partners from necessary data integration. The gap in protection adoption among SMEs does not stem from a lack of awareness but from implementation failures due to high costs.

Long-term stability therefore depends on collective resilience mechanisms that reduce costs per firm and generate positive effects that individual investments cannot achieve. Cybersecurity is no longer a mere technical cost, but a fundamental requirement for participation in the modern digital economy.

The study depends on the scope and quality of the published evidence. The coding reflects the researchers' interpretive engagement, in line with reflexive thematic analysis, but other researchers might produce somewhat different thematic structures. The study does not include primary data. The CEE dimension is limited by the small number of empirical studies on ransomware and SMEs focused on the region. The proposals require empirical testing.

Future research should empirically test P1 through P5 using firm-level and ecosystem-level data, ideally through multimethodological designs combining survey approaches and case studies. Longitudinal studies tracking the recovery trajectories of SMEs after ransomware attacks would be particularly valuable.

Comparative analyses across different regulatory regimes, sectors, and European subregions, including CEE, would reveal the boundary conditions of the findings. Measuring cascading costs at the ecosystem level remains an open methodological challenge. Research into the specific risk profile of SMEs in CEE, combining the region's rapid digitalization trajectory with its institutional and market structure, represents a gap that closing would benefit both academia and practice.

Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) usage statement

ChatGPT (version 5.0) and Google Gemini (version 3 Deep Think) were used responsibly in data analysis. After this process, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and assume full responsibility for the content of this article.

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